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Pīr Muḥammad Garabāghī

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Abstract: Pīr Muḥammad Garabāghī was born, lived, and practiced Sufism in the Magsudlu village in the present-day Aghdam region in the historical province of Ganja-Garabagh. Studying his life, it is identified that in the 16th century, Magsudlu village was one of the respected and the largest semi-nomadic villages in Garabagh. Part of the residents of Magsudlu village planted on the banks of the Jirgis River (now the Gulyatag River), which passes through the territory of the present Garapirimli village, and in the summer they went to the Lachin-Kalbajar mountains for pastures.

The father of Pīr Muḥammad Garabāghī was named Sultan Aḥmad and his grandfather's name was Shaykh Junayd. Both Shaykh Junayd and Sultan Aḥmad lived in Magsudlu village. However, their ancestors were considered to be both Sayyeds and descendants of the famous Sufi Shams-i Tabrīzī. This information is given particularly at the beginning and end of the copies of Pīr Muḥammad's "Manāqibnāma."

The history of Khalwatiyya in Garabagh begins with the formation of the Karaaghaj khangah by Dada 'Omar Rovshanī and his guidance activity there. Dada 'Omar Rovshanī was the caliph of Sayyed Yaḥyā Shirvānī, a Sufi scholar and murshid, who is considered the second Pīr/founder of the Khalwatiyya. Sayyed Yaḥyā sent him to the Garabagh region and instructed him to guide the Turkmen-Tarakama semi-nomadic villages there. His favorite caliph, Ibrāhim Gulshanī Bardāyī, was engaged in guidance activity in both Garabagh and Tabriz. Both Sufis were pearls of Garabagh and were as well known as Sufi poets.

Khalwatiyya society of Garabagh continued as a branch of Rovshanī through the guidance of Dada 'Omar Rovshanī, and most of the subsequent Shaykhs benefited from this branch. It is said that Shaykh 'Abd al-Ghafar, the first Shaykh of Pīr Muḥammad, was also from Rovshanī branch. It is noted that Shāh Gubad Shirvānī also met Dada 'Omar Rovshanī in his early youth. Therefore, researchers note that Pīr Muḥammad was a Rovshanī, Khalwatiyya Shaykh. The Sufi activity started by the Khalwatīs in Garabagh did not stop and has survived in various forms until our times.

Keywords: Garabagh, Pīr Muḥammad, Garapirimli, Khalwatiyya, Sufism

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Pir Məhəmməd Qarabaği

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Pir Məhəmməd Qarabaği XVI əsrdə Qarabağın sayılıb-seçilən, böyük obalarından biri olan Maqsudlu obasında anadan olmuş, yaşamış və təsəvvüfi fəaliyyət göstərmişdir. Araşdırma zamanı Maqsudlu obasının bir hissəsinin indiki Qarapirimli kəndi ərazisindən keçən Cırgıs çayının (indiki Gülyataq çayı) kənarında əkin əkdiyini, yayda Laçın-Kəlbəcər dağlarına yaylaq üçün çıxdıqlarını öyrəndik.

Qarabağlı Pir Məhəmmədin ulu babaları həm seyid, həm də məşhur sufi Şəms Təbrizinin nəslindən hesab olunur. Xüsusilə Pir Məhəmmədin "Mənaqibnamə"sinin nüsxələrinin girişində və sonunda belə məlumatlar verilir.

Qarabağda xəlvətiliyin tarixi Dədə Ömər Rövşəninin Qarağac xanəqahını qurması və orada irşad fəaliyyəti ilə başlayır. Dədə Ömər Rövşəni xəlvətiliyin ikinci piri hesab olunan, təsəvvüf alimi və mürşid Seyid Yəhya Şirvaninin xəlifəsidir. Seyid Yəhya onu Qarabağ bölgəsinə göndərmiş, oradakı türkməntərəkmə obalarını irşad etməklə vəzifələndirmişdir. Onun ən sevimli xəlifəsi Bərdəli İbrahim Gülşəni həm Qarabağda, həm də Təbrizdə irşad fəaliyyəti göstərmişdir. Hər iki sufi Qarabağın incisi olub, sufi-şair kimi də tanınmışdır.

Qarabağ xəlvətiliyi Dədə Ömər Rövşəni yolu ilə rövşənilik qolu kimi davam etmiş, sonrakı əksər şeyxlər bu qoldan bəhrələnmişdir. Pir Məhəmmədin ilk şeyxi Şeyx Əbdülqafarın da rövşəni qolundan olduğu bildirilir. Şah Qubad Şirvaninin də ilk gənclik illərində Dədə Ömər Rövşəni ilə görüşdüyü məlumdur. Ona görə tədqiqatçılar Pir Məhəmmədin rövşəni/xəlvəti şeyxi olduğunu qeyd edirlər. Xəlvətillərin Qarabağda başladığı təsəvvüfi fəaliyyət kəsilməmiş, müxtəlif formalarda indiyə qədər varlığını qorumuşdur.

Açar sözlər: Qarabağ, Şəms Təbrizi, Pir Məhəmməd, Qarapirimli, Xəlvətilik.

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Introduction

One of the first historical regions where Islam spread is the territory of Azerbaijan. It is studied from the historical sources that during the reign of Caliph ‘Umar Ibn al-Khattāb, agreements were signed with local rulers, and the locals were treated more mildly compared to the way the previous imperial powers treated them. It is also known that letters sent from Azerbaijan played a key role in the writing of the Holy Qur’an during the reign of Caliph ‘Uthmān Ibn Affān. It is known that Uwais al-Qaranī, one of the first followers during the reign of Caliph ‘Alī Ibn Abū Tālib and who participated in Muslim marches, was martyred and buried in Azerbaijan. Thus, in the first years of Islam, the territory and population of Azerbaijan are at the center of events.¹

As the Companions were replaced by the followers and the followers by the followers, and Islam spread to wider areas, new scientific and cultural centers and schools began to emerge. Sufism, as a branch of science that studies the psychological state and mystical moods of Muslims, emerges at this stage. Literally, “Sufism” is derived from the verb “*taṣawwuf*” (wearing wool) in connection with the wearing of wool by Sufis, and was used as the infinitive form of that verb. Therefore, those who follow the path of Sufism are also called “Sufis” and “*mutaṣawwif*” European authors, on the other hand, tried to connect philosophy and mysticism in a sense with Sufism.

However, the term “Sufism” is also used because the terms “Eastern philosophy” and “Islamic mysticism” do not fully meet the term “*taṣawwuf*.”²

Analytical approaches to historical sources indicate that Sufism was in fact an institutionalized theoretical trend that encouraged the Turks, who followed a transhumance lifestyle, and the Mongols and other Turkic groups that came with them, to convert to Islam. While both the Arabs and the Persians preferred to study and practice Islam through books, the Turks and Mongols embraced it orally and through conversations. This was especially conditioned by the lifestyle of the Turks.³

Throughout its history, Sufism has passed through two main stages: the stage of *taṣawwuf* and the stage of sects. The spread of Sufism in Azerbaijan began at the stage of *taṣawwuf*, in the 9th-10th centuries. During the transition to sectarianism beginning from the 13th century, two main sects emerged from the school of asceticism in Azerbaijan: Safavidism in Ardabil and Khalwatiyya in Shamākhī. This book tells about the secret Shaykh of Garabagh Pīr Muḥammad, the “*Manāqibnāma*” written about him and the people and places mentioned in the *manāqib*.

Pīr Muḥammad was a Khalwatiyya Shaykh who lived and practiced Sufism in Garabagh in the first half of the 16th century.⁴ The descendants of Pīr

¹ Fariz Xəlilli and Şəhla Xəlilli, “Xəlvəti mürşidi Yusif Müskürinin silsilənəməsi”, *Tarixi yerlər və Abidələr I Beynəlxalq Quba Simpoziumu Materialları*, ed. Fariz Xəlilli. Bakı: im.print, (2020), 205.

² Reşat, Öngören, “Tasavvuf”, *TDV İslam Ansiklopedisi*, 40, 2011, 119.

³ Xəlilli and Xəlilli, “Xəlvəti mürşidi Yusif Müskürinin silsilənəməsi”, 205.

⁴ Ahmet Ögke, “Feyzullah Efendi'nin Tasavvufi Silsilesi ve Seçeresi”, *Erzurumlu Şeyhülislam Seyyid Feyzullah Efendi Sempozyumu Tebliğleri*, ed. Ömer Kara, Erzurum, (2015), 121.

Muhammad, known as the “Gara Pirim” and the “Gara Shaykh” are related to famous Sufi Shams-i Tabrīzī (Turkish copy:1). His grandson, Feyzullah Efendi succeeded to the rank of Shaykh al-Islam, one of the highest positions in the Ottoman Empire, and became a teacher of the sultan's children.¹ In the following period, his descendants were closely involved in the socio-political activities of the Ottoman state. Currently, the collection of Pīr Muḥammad's grandson Feyzullah Efendi is reserved in the National Library, located in the Fatih district of Istanbul. A collection of Feyzullah Efendi's manuscripts is preserved in the library as well. The Turkish copy of “Manāqibnāma” is in that collection. Feyzullah Efendi also wrote a treatise named “Silsilanāma”, which introduces the genealogy of his family.² In this book, we provide information about the life and activity of Pīr Muḥammad of Garabagh based on both “Manāqibnāma” and “Silsilanāma” treatises.

Life of Pīr Muḥammad Garabāghī

The grandson of Pīr Muḥammad Garabāghī, the Ottoman Shaykh al-Islam Feyzullah Efendi writes his genealogy as follows: Feyzullah Efendi, son of Shaykh Muḥammad, son of Habib Muḥammad, son of Pīr Muḥammad, son of Sultan Aḥmad, son of Shaykh Junayd.³

Pīr Muḥammad was born, lived, and practiced Sufism in the village of Magsudlu in the present-day Aghdam region of the Ganja-Garabagh principality (1501-1747). When studying his life, it becomes clear that in the 16th century, the village of Magsudlu was one of the largest, well-known villages in Garabagh. A part of Magsudlu village was planting on the bank of the Jirgis river (now Gulyatag river) passing through the territory of the present Garapirimli village, and in summer they were going to the Lachin-Kalbajar mountains for pastures.

Pīr Muḥammad's father's name was Sultan Aḥmad and his grandfather's name was Shaykh Junayd.⁴ Both Shaykh Junayd and Sultan Aḥmad lived in the village of Magsudlu. However, their ancestors are considered to be both descendants of Sayyeds and the famous Sufi Shams Tabrizi.⁵ In particular, this information is given at the beginning and end of the copies of the “Manāqibnāma” (Turkish copy: 1).

We do not know even the approximate date of the birth of Pīr Muḥammad. However, it can be assumed that he was born at the end of the 15th century. Pīr Muḥammad's childhood was remembered with very interesting events, and the author of “Manāqibnāma” included some of those events in his stories. It is said that Pīr Muḥammad saw people who sinned as children as savages and ran away from them. His father, Sultan Aḥmad, was very worried about this and brought him to Shaykh ‘Abd al-Ghafar, who worked in a neighboring village. Professor

¹ Mehmet Serhan Tayşi, “Feyzullah Efendi”, *TDV İslam Ansiklopedisi*, 12, 1995, 527.

² Ömer Kara and Ahmet Ögke, “Feyzullah Efendi'nin Kendi Kaleminden Şeceresini ve Silsilesini Anlattığı Risale: Tenkitli Neşir”, *Erzurumlu Şeyhülislam Seyyid Feyzullah Efendi Sempozyumu Tebliğleri*, ed. Ömer Kara, Erzurum, (2015), 133.

³ Ögke, “Feyzullah Efendi'nin Tasavvufi Silsilesi ve Şeceresi”, 119.

⁴ Ögke, “Feyzullah Efendi'nin Tasavvufi Silsilesi ve Şeceresi”, 120.

⁵ *Ibid.*, 132.

Aḥmad Ogke mentions that Pīr Muḥammad was seven years old at the time, according to the phrase “sinn al-tamyīz.”¹

Shaykh ‘Abd al-Ghafar is the teacher, first Shaykh and murshid of Pīr Muḥammad. Shaykh ‘Abd al-Ghafar's name appears in four stories in the “Manāqibnāma”. The “Silsilanāma” also provides information about him. There is no information about him in other sources. It is known that Shaykh ‘Abd al-Ghafar died in 1527.² The story indicates that Shaykh ‘Abd al-Ghafar lives in Garabagh, in a neighboring village not mentioned in the source, half a day's distance from the present-day village of Garapirimli in Aghdam region, and works as a Shaykh in the sect of Khalwatiyya. With the consent of Sultan Aḥmad, Shaykh ‘Abd al-Ghafar deals with the psychology and pedagogy of Pīr Muḥammad.

Shaykh ‘Abd al-Ghafar bequeathed his prostration and the position of the sect not to his children, but to Pīr Muḥammad, with whom he was convinced that he was the possessor of discovery and miracle. Even Shaykh ‘Abd al-Ghafar foresaw that Pīr Muḥammad's disciples would be more numerous, widespread and that he would rise to a higher level of perfection. There are two stories in the “Manāqibnāma” about the permission of the caliphate and the story of Pīr Muḥammad's succession of Shaykh ‘Abd al-Ghafar in the series. Shāh Gubad Shirānī is the second Shaykh and murshid of Pīr Muḥammad. Pīr Muḥammad met him in 1543 and received permission to the caliphate in the sect of Khalwatiyya. It becomes clear from the story that Shāh Gubad was the most important figure in the field of Sufism in the whole Caucasus at that time. At the meeting, Shāh Gubad saw that Pīr Muḥammad was ready for guidance, a man of discovery and greatness, aware of the secrets of eighteen thousand worlds. He gifts Pīr Muḥammad a walking stick and a praying mat and allows him to guide the sect. It is understood that Shāh Gubad was very old at that time because he referred to Pīr Muḥammad as “my child”. Shāh Gubad died fifteen or eighteen days after Pīr Muḥammad's return to Garabagh.

One of the main reasons for Pīr Muḥammad's visit to Shāh Gubad was that he spoke a language that was not available in Persian, Arabic, Turkish, or Assyrian during the conquest. Shāh Gubad said that he knew about that language and that Baba Mansur Varandali spoke that language. However, Pīr Muḥammad realizes that Shāh Gubad does not know the language and does not talk about it much. The story also reveals the name of another Shaykh whom Shāh Gubad appointed as caliph besides Pīr Muḥammad. He was Oruj Amīr from Dagestan. It is also indicated in the second story that after the death of Shāh Gubad, some of the disciples from Shirvan came to Garabagh, to Pīr Muḥammad, served him, and solved their problems with his advice.

Feyzullah Efendi writes in “Silsilanāma” that Pīr Muḥammad, who followed the will of Shāh Gubad, tried to follow the right of guidance and was known as “Gara Shaykh” at that time, became a Sufi-traditionalist of people by his words, reactions and behavior and was engaged with their education. As the

¹ Ibid., 120.

² Ibid., 120.

number of his disciples increased, government officials and other people competed with each other to ensure that he did not fail in his service. Many of his wise quotes and manāqib were known, spread from language to language. Even works about this have been written in Arabic and Turkic languages. During his lifetime, there was nobody from both the jurists and the common people who did not recognize him and accepted his guardianship.¹

Pīr Muḥammad met Shāh Tahmasib (1524-1576), the eldest son of Shāh Ismail I, the second king of the Safavid state of Azerbaijan, in the city of Qazvin. Shāh Tahmasib invited Pīr Muḥammad to Qazvin when he heard that his popularity among the Garabagh Sufis was growing, his disciples were increasing, and the volume of his works was expanding. Pīr Muḥammad sensed Shāh Tahmasib's intention in advance and comes to Qazvin himself. In Qazvin, Shāh Tahmasib tested Pīr Muḥammad several times and became convinced of his perfect mentorship. He instructs that no one should interfere in the affairs of Pīr Muḥammad.

Pīr Muḥammad from Garabagh died in 1549.² He was buried in the khanagah of Garapirimli village in Garabagh near the graves of his father and grandfather (Shaykh Junayd and his son Sultan Aḥmad), and a tomb was built over his grave. The tomb was visited by the people of Garabagh in later times, even during the Soviet era. Garapirimli village and the tomb of Pīr Muḥammad, which have been under the control of the occupying army of the Republic of Armenia since 1993, were liberated on November 20, 2020, by our victorious army under the leadership of the Commander-in-Chief of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev. In the future, archaeological excavations will be carried out in the khanagah and tomb and the monument will be restored.

The Succession of Khalwatiyya of Pīr Muḥammad Garabāghī

The Silsilaname (The Book of Succession) is a written document that goes from the Prophet Muḥammad to the last Shaykh and indicates the succession of Sufis. This document also showed how the Shaykhs knew their succession and its authenticity. Naturally, these documents have not appeared all of a sudden, they were gradually formed and passed down from generation to generation. It was possible to compile the series of Khatwatiyya based on Pīr Muḥammad's meeting with Shāh Gubad Shirvānī in 1543 and obtaining permission. As Yousef Muskurī mentioned, all poles pass the truth from generation to generation after one another. The pole of the prophets is the Prophet Muḥammad (pbuh), as he is the seal of the prophets. The pole of the saints is 'Alī (pbuh), as he is the last of the four caliphs. The succession of inspiration passed from our Prophet Muḥammad (peace be upon him) to 'Alī (peace be with him) is as follows:

Ḥasan al-Basrī;
Habīb al-'Ajamī;
Dāvūd al-Ṭā'ī;

¹ Ögke, "Feyzullah Efendi'nin Tasavvufi Silsilesi ve Şeceresi", 121.

² Ibid., 121.

Ma'rūf al-Karkhī;
Sarī al-Saqāfī;
Junayd al-Baghdadī;
Mumshād al-Dinavārī;
Muḥammad al-Dinavārī;
Muḥammad al-Bakrī;
Vahy al-dīn Gāzi “Omar Bakrī;
Abu al-najīb Suhrawardī;
Qutbaddin Abhārī;
Ruknaddin Muḥammad Najashī;
Shihāb al-dīn Tabrīzī;
Sayyed Jamāl al-dīn;
Shaykh Ibrāhim Zāhid;
Akhī Muḥammad;
“Omar Avaxili Shirvānī;
Molla ‘Alī Malhamī Shirvānī (Akhi Mirim);
Haji ‘Izz al-dīn Shirvānī;
Pīr Şadr al-dīn;
Abū Shaykh Aḥmad;
Ibn Abū al-Gāsim;
Sayyed Yaḥyā Badkūbī (May God sanctify his secrets);
Yousef Muskurī (May god bless him)¹

After Yousef Muskurī, Muḥammad Rukkī, after the latest Shāh Gubad Shirvānī has continued the succession. Shāh Gubad has passed the succession to Pīr Muḥammad.

The history of Khalwatiyya in Garabagh begins with the construction of the Garaagaj khanagah by Dada ‘Omar Rovshanī and his guidance there. Dada ‘Omar Rovshanī is the caliph of Sayyed Yaḥyā Shirvānī, a Sufi scholar and murshid, who was considered the second shrine of Khalwatiyya. He was from the Aydın region of the Republic of Turkey and completed his spiritual tour in the Baku khanagah. Sayyed Yaḥyā sent him to Garabagh region and instructed him to guide the Turkmen-Tarakama villages there.² Dede ‘Omar Rovshanī’s guidance was supported by Aghgoyunlu ruler Uzun Hasan and his wife Seljuk Khātun. The Tabriz khanagah was established for Dada ‘Omar Rovshanī and began to operate there.³ His favorite caliph, Ibrāhim Gulshanī Bardalī, was a guide in both Garabagh and Tabriz. Both Sufis were considered pearls of Garabagh and were known as Sufi poets. Their Dīwāns and Mathnawī are important works of Sufi literature. Ibrāhim Gulshanī moved to Cairo, Egypt after the Safavids came to power in Tabriz. The Cairo khanagah of Khalwatiyya,

¹ Юсуф Мускури Ширвани, Изъяснение тайн желающим пройти пут суфизма, Иерархия творений. Стокгольм: «СА&СС Пресс», 336 с., (2006), 122-123.

² Mahmud Cemaleddin al-Hulvī, *Lemezât-ı Hulviyye ez Lemezât-ı Ulviyye*, ed. Mehmet Serhan Tayşi, (İstanbul: Marmara Üniversitesi İlahiyat Fakültesi Vakfı, 1993), 514.

³ Ayşe Atıcı Arayancan, “Akkoyunlu Sarayında Bir Begüm ya da Mehd-i Ulya: Selçukşah Begüm”, *Avrasiya Uluslararası Araştırmalar Dergisi*, Cilt: 7, Sayı: 20, (2019), 8.

which still retains its grandeur, was built for him.¹ The Garabagh Khatwatiyya continued as a Rovshanīyya branch through Dada ‘Omar Rovshanī, and most subsequent Shaykhs benefited from this branch. It is said that Shaykh ‘Abd al-Ghafar, the first Shaykh of Pīr Muḥammad, was also from Rovshanīyya branch. It is noted that Shāh Gubad Shirvānī also met Dada Rovshanī in his early youth. Therefore, researchers believe that Pīr Muḥammad was a Rovshanīyya/Khalwatiyya Shaykh.² The Sufism activity started by Khalwatiyya in Garabagh has not stopped, it has preserved its existence in various forms until now.

Followers of Pīr Muḥammad Garabāghī

Pīr Muḥammad had two sons from Zeynab khanum: Shaykh Walīyaddin Muḥammad and Shaykh Habib Muḥammad.³ After the death of Pīr Muḥammad, his eldest son Shaykh Walīyaddin Muḥammad took the position of Shaykh in Garapirimli khanagah. In “Manāqibnāma” the name of Shaykh Walīyaddin Muḥammad is mentioned in a story. His nickname is “Walī Gaga” and his name is “Walī Muḥammad”. He was welcoming science students from Ganja, offering food and services to guests.

Shaykh Walīyaddin had a tough temperament and a strong charm. At that time, Garabagh disciples gathered around him. Safavid oppression and deportation of the Sunni population increased during this period. Part of the family, along with the villages of Garabagh, was relocated around the city of Astarabad in Iran. At the end of the 17th century, Feyzullah Efendi wrote that some of the Shaykh's descendants also lived in Astarabad. He and a Sufi family is known as “Dada Efendi” from the family of Pīr Muḥammad had to move to Crimea, where they settled.

After the death of Shaykh Walīyaddin, he was buried in Garapirimli next to his father Pīr Muḥammad.⁴

Shaykh Walīyaddin's brother Shaykh Habib Muḥammad took his place in the sect in Garapirimli khanagah after his death. Shaykh Habib Muḥammad was orphaned when his father died when he was a child. He married the daughter of Akkashoglu Huseyn agha from Magsudlu village. His grandson, Feyzullah Efendi, described Habib Muḥammad as “a devout, ascetic, a person who turned to his Lord with all his heart, turned away from worldly luxuries, and continued to recite accurately and continuously in matters of worship and secrecy.” Those who attended his sects and ceremonies witnessed that his prayer was mustahabb and that he performed many miracles. Habib Muḥammad married Heyrannisa khanum, the daughter of Sayyed Muḥammad Sharif Efendi's son Sayyed Muḥammad Amīn, known as “Gizilgaya Sayyeds” in Garabagh, and his son Shaykh Muḥammad was born from that lady. He died in 1616 at the age of eighty and was buried near his father's grave in Garapirimli.⁵ Feyzullah Efendi wrote, “Our Shaykhs were in agreement that the lineage of our ancestors had reached

¹ al-Hulvī, *Lemez-at-ı Hulviyye ez Lemez-at-ı Ulviyye*, 514.

² Ögke, “Feyzullah Efendi'nin Tasavvufi Silsilesi ve Şeceresi”, 131.

³ Ibid., 121.

⁴ Ögke, “Feyzullah Efendi'nin Tasavvufi Silsilesi ve Şeceresi”, 121.

⁵ Ibid., 122.

the state of bliss. In the area where they lived, they were known as “Sayyeds of Gizilgaya”. Gizilgaya is a famous place in Garabagh.¹ According to the oral information from Prof. Dr. Shikar Gasimov from the village of Jijimli, the tomb of Malik Ajdar and Kar Gunbaz in the village of Jijimli are located on Gizilgaya Hill. It is known that these tombs belonged to the Sayyed families. The famous Sufi Mir Hamza Sayyed Nigari is also from that village.

After Habib Muḥammad, his eldest son Shaykh Mustafa sat in the post of the sect in Garapirimli khanagah according to family tradition. He was a righteous man, a devotee, a devout man who obeyed God Almighty and followed in his father's footsteps. During the Ottoman occupation of Garabagh, the local Sunni population, especially the Sufis, seemed to have breathed a sigh of relief. However, the withdrawal of the Ottoman state from the region with the Treaty of Qasri-Shirin (1639) again created problems. After prolonged pressure, Shaykh Mustafa sought a way out and decided to emigrate with his relatives, disciples, and subjects. They leave their homes, their lands, their gardens. They just take their luggage and leave with their families. They stopped in Erzurum and decided to settle there.

Feyzullah Efendi mentions that his uncle Shaykh Mustafa and his father Shaykh Muḥammad met with the Ottoman sultan Murad 4th (1623-1640) and received permission to settle. Sultan Murad 4th allowed them to settle in Erzurum and Erzinjan and acquire land and pastures for cultivation. Shaykh Mustafa died in 1666 and was buried in the cemetery on the western outskirts of Erzurum.²

After Shaykh Mustafa, his brother Shaykh Muḥammad Efendi took the post of sect in Erzurum. He was also appointed Mufti of Erzurum during his service as a murshid. He continued both his spiritual guidance and his external public duty together for 20 years. According to Feyzullah Efendi his father built a building near the house of Shaykh Muḥammad. He used to pray here five times a day. After the morning prayer, he would sit for a while, and his friends and disciples would accompany him by remembering Allahu ta'âlâ in accordance with the Sunnah and reciting his prayers. Then they would perform nafila prayers in the mosque. His father used to come home from there and give fatwas to people. He had reached the level of guardianship and had performed many miracles.

Shaykh Muḥammad Efendi, who was able to write with calligraphy, personally wrote down the Holy Qur'an and other books. He wrote beautiful poems that contained a lot of different information. He built many mosques, bridges, and water canals in the area where he lived.

Shaykh Muḥammad Efendi has been married three times. His first wife, Sharifa Khatun, was the daughter of Mullah Murtaza Jannati, the Mufti of Erzurum, a descendant of the famous scholar Hanafi Garabaghi. She is also the mother of the Ottoman Shaykh-ul-Islam Feyzullah. After the death of Sharifa Khatun, Shaykh Muḥammad of Erzurum married a daughter of a family, but because she died soon, he married another lady.

Shaykh Muḥammad Efendi died on March 11, 1693, at the age of eighty-six. When he was ill, his son Shaykh-ul-Islam Feyzullah Efendi, who lived in

¹ Ögke, “Feyzullah Efendi'nin Tasavvufi Silsilesi ve Şeceresi”, 125.

² Ögke, “Feyzullah Efendi'nin Tasavvufi Silsilesi ve Şeceresi”, 123.

Istanbul, came to Erzurum and attended his funeral. Shaykh Muḥammad Efendi was buried next to his brother Shaykh Mustafa in the cemetery at the western exit of Erzurum.¹

The grandson of Pîr Muḥammad was Feyzullah Efendi (1639-1703), Shaykh-ul-Islam of the Ottoman Empire. He received his education from his father and close relatives, and then from the well-known scholar Shaykh Muḥammad Vani. Feyzullah Efendi, who was a teacher in Istanbul, was appointed as a teacher to Sultan Mustafa II (1695-1703), the son of Sultan Muḥammad IV. Feyzullah Efendi, who rose to various positions, was also the teacher of Sultan Aḥmad III (1703-1730). Although Feyzullah Efendi was appointed Shaykh-ul-Islam in 1688, he remained in this position for only seventeen days. The country was engulfed in riots and chaos. After Sultan Mustafa II came to power, he was re-appointed Shaykh-ul-Islam in 1695. Sultan Mustafa II loved Feyzullah Efendi as his teacher, respected his decisions and fatwas, and created conditions for him to interfere in the affairs of the state. Feyzullah Efendi, who had been a Shaykh-ul-Islam for eight years, was assassinated in Edirne in 1703 as a result of the uprisings in Istanbul and then in Edirne.²

Feyzullah Efendi wrote many works in Arabic and Turkic. He built a mosque, a madrasa, a Qur'an classroom, a school and a bathhouse in Erzurum, a hadith classroom in Damascus, a fountain and a sabil in Edirne, a mosque in Makkah, a madrasah and library in Madina, a madrasah, library, mosque, school, house for teachers and fountains in the Fatih district of Istanbul. The complex in the Fatih district, known as the Fezziyya Hadith School, is now the Istanbul National Library. There is a collection of Feyzullah Efendi's manuscripts in that library. The collection consists of books by Feyzullah Efendi. There are many manuscripts about Garabagh in this collection, which need to be studied in the future.³

Feyzullah Efendi had many children. At the beginning of the 18th century, Feyzullah's family was acquitted and returned to high government positions. His son Mustafa Efendi FeyzullahEfendizadeh was an Ottoman Shaykh-ul-Islam in 1736-1745.⁴ He participated in the discussions opened by Nadir Shāh Afshar (1736-1747) to accept the Jafari sect as the fifth sect.⁵ Another son of Feyzullah Efendi, Murtaza Feyzullah Efendizadeh, was an Ottoman Shaykh in 1750-1755. In the following years, the Feyzullah Efendizadeh generation played an important role among the Ottoman aristocratic families. The path of science and Sufism, which began in Garabagh, extended to the central administration of the Ottoman Empire.

¹ Ögke, "Feyzullah Efendi'nin Tasavvufi Silsilesi ve Şeceresi", 124.

² Tayşi, "Feyzullah Efendi", 527-528.

³ Ibid., 527-528.

⁴ Mehmet İpşirli, "Mustafa Efendi Feyzullah Efendizade", *TDV İslam Ansiklopedisi*, 31, 2006, 297.

⁵ Uğur, Kurtaran, "Yeni Kaynakların Işığında Sultan I. Mahmud Dönemi Osmanlı-İran İlişkileri (1731-1747)", *"History Studies" International Journal of History*, v. 3/3, (2011), 190.

“Manāqibnāma” by Pīr Muḥammad of Garabagh

We have been able to discover three copies of “Manāqibnāma” of Pīr Muḥammad of Garabagh. These manuscripts are coded 2142/6 in the “Feyzullah Efendi collection” of the National Library of the Republic of Turkey in Istanbul, B-6622 coded in the Institute of Manuscripts of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences and copy from the private collection of Ruslan Mammadov Anvaroglu, living in Duruja village of Gabala region.

The following is a palaeographic description of these copies involved in the codicological study from our side has been provided below. We conditionally called the copies “Turkish copy”, “Baku copy” and “Duruja copy”. When transliterating the text, the “Turkish copy” was taken as the main copy.

1. Turkey copy.¹ This copy is kept in the “Feyzullah Efendi collection” of the National Library in Istanbul, Turkey. Its name is mentioned as “Menakib-i Pīr Muḥammad Ganjavi”. The copy consists of 25 pages, its size is 21.6x14 cm. It is written on Venetian-lined watercolor paper. The text is black, the narrative titles are in red ink. Each page consists of 15 lines. Its cover is leather. The text begins: “This treatise, which is from the son of Hadrat Shams Tabrizi, is narrated by Shaykh Pīr Muḥammad al-Ganjavi in some manāqib narrations, Quddusullahi-asraruhul-aziz.” It ends: “They say that we have been commanded to declare it, may God have mercy on us.” The last page of the copy has a stamp stating that it belongs to the “Feyzullah Efendi Collection”. The seal is the foundation seal of the Ottoman Shaykh-ul-Islam Faizullah Efendi. The date is written in the seal as 1112 AH, which is equal to 1700 AD.

2. Baku copy.² The size of this copy, preserved under the code B-6622 at the Institute of Manuscripts named after Muḥammad Fuzuli of ANAS, consists of 27 pages. The title of the copy is written as “Pīr Muḥammad al-Ganjurri - Risale-i Nur”. The size is 20x14 cm. The manuscript is placed in a purple cardboard folder. The manuscript is wrapped in a thin yellow paper. The condition of this paper is unsatisfactory, the edges are torn, and some parts are eaten by insects. There is a letter written on it. On the first page of the yellow paper, there is an inscription that cannot be read in some places: “Baes həyatam, vasila bahayam pedar..... shamayim. Afterward, Huzur-e Sharif, who was exposed to water, became a young man. It is a mistake for me to complain to the Prophet (May God Bless Him) as we are satisfied and content in the name of being a servant, and to show complete confidence in the perfection of education. your servant asks for your blessings”. At the end of this paper, a sentence is written: “The treatise of Sayyedi- ferd Pīrim”.

The paper of the manuscript is blue, linear. The number of lines on the page is different. The text is written in black ink, and the headings of the narrations are crossed out with red ink to distinguish them. The text begins with the words “Bismillahir-Rahmanir-Rahim” and ends with the words “It is narrated that”. The manuscript is incomplete and consists of 26 sources.

¹ *Menākīb-ı Pīr Muhammed Gencevî*, Türkiye Yazma Eserler Kurumu Başkanlığı Millet Yazma Eser Kütüphanesi, Feyzullah Efendi, 2142/6.

² Pīr Məhəmməd əl-Gəncürri, *Risalə*, AMEA Məhəmməd Füzuli adına Əlyazmalar İnstitutu, B-6622.

3. Duruja copy.¹ This copy is from the personal collection of Mammadov Ruslan Anvaroglu, living in Duruja village of the Gabala region. The copy consists of 70 pages. The size is 17x11 cm. It is written in a blue line on a Russian watercolor sheet. Each page consists of 9 lines. The coverage is brown. The text is black, the title of the narration is written in red ink. There is a red punctuation mark between each sentence. On the last page, both the text and the number indicate the year 1245 AH, ie 1829 AD. The text begins: "This treatise is one of the true stories about Shaykh Pīr Muḥammad al-Ganjavi (Qaddasallahi sirrahul-aziz)." He concludes: "Tammāt manāqib-i Shaykh Pīr Muḥammad al-mulaggab bi Gara Pīrim al-Ganjavi der sanagi-dartarihi-alf wa miyateyn wa khamsa wa arbaina minal-hijrati 1245".

These copies, which we obtained for research, were compared and codicological analyzed from a textual point of view. Copies were written by various calligraphers. While copying the faces of the copies, we came across some differences between the texts. Of the copies, the "Turkish copy" and the "Duruja copy" are complete, and the "Baku copy" is incomplete. There are 36 manāqib in the full copies, and 26 manāqib in the "Baku copy". The last 10 manāqib of it are missing. In all three copies, manāqib sources begin with the words "it is narrated that."

We encountered various errors when transliterating the copies. Some words or sentences are forgotten and then given at the edge of the page. This event appears in all three copies. For example, on page 8b of the "Turkey copy", the words "with your breath" were forgotten and the words "with your breath" were forgotten in the sentence "Alhamdulillah, we saw with your eyes that you found a dead life in your time with your breath".

In addition to these features, we were also faced with the phenomenon of replacing words with other words in the copies. We can see the phenomenon of replacing Arabic-Persian words with Turkic words or, conversely, Turkic words with Arabic words. For example, in the 18th manāqib, the word "lisan" in the "Turkey copy" was replaced by the word "dil" in the "Duruja copy". In the 7th manāqib, the word "ayyami-sayf" in the "Turkey copy" was replaced with the word "yaz günlərində" in the "Duruja copy", and the word "yıqarkən" in the "Turkey copy" was replaced with the words "yur ikən" in the "Duruja copy". In the 33rd manāqib, the word "söndürür" in the "Turkey copy" appears as the word "qaraldır" in the "Duruca copy". In the same manāqib, the word "şəm" was replaced by the word "çıraq", and the word "ışqlanır" was replaced by the word "pür ənvar olur".

In addition, some words are written differently in each copy. For example, in the 22nd manāqib, the word "çigidin" in the "Turkish copy" is given as "çəkirdəsin" in the "Baku copy" and "çəkidağın" in the "Duruja copy". Here we are talking about "melon seeds". In the 34th manāqib, Shāh Tahmasib's name is mentioned as Shāh Tahmas in the "Duruja copy".

¹ Şeyx Pīr Məhəmməd əl-Gəncəvi həzrətləri Qaddəsallahi sirrahul-əzizin əssah rəvayətlə bəzi mənāqibindəndir, Ruslan Məmmədovun şəxsi kolleksiyası.

In general, the “Turkey copy” and the “Duruja copy” are very clear, neat, and readable. The “Baku copy” is untidy compared to other copies. As for the sentences, the sentences of the “Turkey copy” and the “Baku copy” are more the same. While comparing the “Duruja copy” with other copies, we came across some differences in the sentences.

Conclusion

It is very important to study the Garapirimli khanagah, one of the material cultures of Garabagh's spiritual values, to read its inscriptions, and to prepare a restoration conservation project. Garapirimli village is located in the territory of Aghdam region, was liberated from occupation in November 2020. Garapirimli village was formed by the settlement of his descendants and disciples around the khanagah belonging to Gara Pirim. Apparently, Gara Pirim is the nickname of the famous Sufi scholar, saint Pīr Muḥammad Garabāghī. He is a descendant of the famous Sufi Shamsi Tabrizi. Gara Pirim was a contemporary of Shāh Tahmasib and met with Shāh. After his death, his khanagah was always active and played an important role in the construction of the spirituality of Garabagh. In the Muslim world, Garabagh and Gara Pirim are mentioned together.

An in-depth study of Islamic in Garabagh heritage weakens the arguments of Armenian vandals and presents historical realities to the world community. Recently, “Miras” Public Union, with the support of the Foundation for the Propagation of Moral Values, published the book “Manāqibnāma of Pīr Muḥammad of Garabagh”. The book presents the events that took place in the Gara Pirim Khanate as Sufi stories. The work, which describes the spiritual life of Garabagh in the 16th century, also provides interesting toponymic and ethnographic information. Obviously, the grandson of the Gara Pirim was Feyzullah Efendi, the Shaykh-ul-Islam of the Ottoman state and a teacher of the two sultans. His sons Mustafa and Murtaza Feyzullah Efendizadeh were also Ottoman Shaykh-ul-Islam. Many of the manuscripts they brought from Garabagh are preserved in the manuscript collection of Feyzullah Efendi at the Istanbul National Library. The Gara Pirim case, which is the key to a lot of valuable historical information, must be studied scientifically from an academic point of view. The study of the Gara Pirim Khanagah is of great importance in the issue of the national identity of Garabagh.

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